

Ini dari kerjaan yang di AFM

Please check comment section, untuk kerjaan baru, mana yang harus elo ganti di kalkulasinya

Calculation of adhesive force. The adhesive forces which consist of electrostatic force and van der Waals interactions are calculated based on the following literature.^[5, 6] In a supplementary materials of preceding work [7], detail of calculations are described to obtain the total adhesive forces which is the sum of electrostatic and van der Waals forces. In contrast to the preceding work, in his work we compare the total adhesive forces of two distinguished systems: samples which contain (i) Poly-L-lysine (PLL) substrates and poly(N- isopropyl acrylamide) (PNIPAM) gel particles in water; (ii) (3-Aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (APTES) substrates and pNIPAM gel particles in water.

For the system (i), PLL surface potential, $\phi_s = 60mV$, Zeta potential of particles obtained through the measurement (for example for radius of 155 nm), $\phi_p = -45mV$, permittivity $\epsilon_0 = 8.854187817 \times 10^{-12}C^2N^{-1}m^{-2}$, $\epsilon_w = 78.5C^2N^{-1}m^{-2}$, distance range $r_s = 10^{-6}nm$ and $r_p = 10^{-7}nm$, and approximated $r_d = 10^{-9}nm$ yields electrostatic forces $F \approx -0.39 nN$, in which the negative value represents attractive interaction. For permittivity of PLL $\epsilon_s = 83C^2N^{-1}m^{-2}$, pNIPAM $\epsilon_p = 2.2593C^2N^{-1}m^{-2}$, refractive index of PLL $n_s = 1.37$, water $n_w = 1.3325$, pNIPAM $n_p = 1.52$, natural frequency $\nu_e = 1GHz$, $k_b = 1.38064852 \times 10^{-23}m^2kg s^{-2}K^{-1}$, the temperature $T = 298.14 K$ and Planck constant $h = 6.62607004 \times 10^{-34}m^2kg/s$ yield the adhesive force with magnitude of $-0.39311209 nN$. The aforementioned calculations are repeated for other pNIPAM particles : pNIPAM 161.5 nm with $\phi_p = -46mV$ and 208 nm with $\phi_p = -42mV$.

For the other system (ii), APTES surface potential, $\phi_s = 50mV$, Zeta potential of particles obtained through the measurement (for example for radius of 155 nm), $\phi_p = -45mV$, permittivity $\epsilon_0 = 8.854187817 \times 10^{-12}C^2N^{-1}m^{-2}$, $\epsilon_w = 78.5C^2N^{-1}m^{-2}$, distance range $r_s = 10^{-6}nm$ and $r_p = 10^{-7}nm$, and approximated $r_d = 10^{-9}nm$ yields electrostatic forces $F \approx -0.325 nN$. For permittivity of APTES $\epsilon_s = 87C^2N^{-1}m^{-2}$, refractive index of APTES $n_s = 1.4225$, and the equal-remaining parameters as the system (i) yield the adhesive force with magnitude $-0.32971203 nN$. Completed results are provided in the following tables:

Things to complete:

Semua particle pNIPAM refractive indexnya 1.52

Kasus A, substrate PLL ($\phi_s = 60mV$, refractive index 1.37)

Radius of particles in nm	Zeta potential ϕ_p (mV)	Adhesive force (nN)
155	-45	-0.39311209
161.5	-46	-0.38469975
208	-42	-0.35982818

Kasus B, substrate APTES ($\phi_s = 50mV$, refractive index 1.4225)

Radius of particles in nm	Zeta potential ϕ_p (mV)	Adhesive force (nN)
155	-45	-0.32971203
161.5	-46	-0.32279059
208	-42	-0.30269987

7. D. Septiadi, et. al. 2020. *Advanced Functional Materials* 202002630R1.